

SOME ISSUES OF DISTINGUISHING EXTORTION FROM ARBITRARINESS

Ergashev Ilyos Urol Ugli

Independent Researcher

of Tashkent State University of Law

E-mail: ergashevilyos7676@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10638069>

Abstract: In law enforcement practice, many issues arise related to the separation of extortion from arbitrariness. This paper examines the signs that make it possible to distinguish extortion from arbitrariness.

Keywords: extortion, arbitrariness, demand, major damage or substantial harm.

In law enforcement practice, questions often arise about the distinction between crimes such as extortion and arbitrariness.

Extortion is defined as a demand for the transfer of someone else's property or the right to someone else's property, the provision of property benefits or the commission of actions of a property nature under threat of violence against the person of the victim or persons close to him, damage or destruction of property. This may also include the destruction, modification, seizure or blocking of the victim's information resources, the disclosure of information that they wish to keep secret, the dissemination of defamatory information about the victim, or the creation of an environment forcing the victim to transfer property or the right to property (according to article 165 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan).

The main direct object of extortion is public relations in the field of property regulation, to which the stolen property belongs. An additional direct object is public relations related to the protection of the personal right of the victim, who is in danger of extortion.

The nature of the mental violence used by the perpetrator causes an additional object of extortion. For example, the threat of violence may concern public relations related to the safety of citizens, and the threat of disclosure of confidential information may affect the honor and dignity of the individual and the right to privacy.

Extortion is a complex composite crime in which the perpetrator simultaneously makes illegal demands on the owner of the property and uses mental violence in the form of threats.

The subjective side of extortion is characterized by direct intent - the perpetrator realizes that he illegally demands the transfer of property, the right to it, or the commission of other property actions under threat of violence against the victim or his relatives and wants to carry out these actions. The subject may be a sane individual who has reached the age of 14.

Arbitrariness is defined as the unauthorized exercise of one's real or perceived right, which leads to significant damage to the rights or legally protected interests of citizens, the state or public interests.

The main direct object of this crime is public relations regulating the process of citizens exercising their rights, including their acquisition, modification and termination. An additional direct object is public relations that ensure the legitimate interests and rights of other citizens or legal entities, as well as the fulfillment of their assigned duties.

On the objective side, arbitrariness manifests itself in the unauthorized exercise of a real or perceived right, which causes significant damage to the legally protected interests of citizens, the state or public interests. This action must cause major damage or substantial harm.

Arbitrariness is committed only through active actions, inaction cannot be considered as arbitrariness. For example, failure to comply with a court decision is not arbitrariness.

On the subjective side, the crime provided for in Article 229 of the Criminal Code is committed with direct or indirect intent regarding the occurrence of criminal consequences described in the text of the article. The motive and purpose of the crime do not matter for its qualification.

Any person who has reached the age of 16 and is not an official can be a subject of arbitrariness[1]. However, if the perpetrator uses his official position to commit arbitrariness, his actions may entail liability under article 205 (Abuse of power or official authority) or Article 206 of the Criminal Code (Abuse of power or official authority), depending on the circumstances of the case.

For arbitrariness, an obligatory sign is the onset of the consequences specified in Article 229 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Consequently, arbitrariness is considered completed at the moment of occurrence of these consequences in the form of major damage or significant harm to the rights or interests of citizens, or to state or public interests. The assessment of significant harm caused by arbitrariness to the victim is subjective and is usually determined by the court. For example, a violation of the

constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens or a violation of public order may be considered a significant harm.

In contrast, extortion is considered completed immediately after making a demand for the transfer of someone else's property or the right to it, the provision of property benefits or the commission of property-related actions backed up by the threat of violence against the victim or his relatives, damage or destruction of property, or destruction, modification, seizure or blocking of information resources of the victim, disclosure of information that the victim wishes to keep secret or spread defamatory information about him, even if the target property has not been transferred.

Extortion is committed with direct intent, while the perpetrator acts for selfish reasons, realizing that he has no legal rights to the required property, and seeks to illegally enrich himself at the expense of the victim or his relatives. He seeks to obtain property free of charge, the right to it, the provision of property benefits or the commission of property actions.

In cases where a person extorts property to which he has a valid or alleged right (for example, if the victim gave this property on loan, on credit, or it is in his temporary custody, etc.), the *corpus delicti* provided for in Article 165 of the Criminal Code is excluded. In such situations, actions can be qualified as arbitrariness (according to Article 229 of the Criminal Code) if they comply with the signs provided for in the law [2].

Extortion involves demanding the transfer of someone else's property or rights to it, the provision of property benefits or the commission of property-related actions. Therefore, the demand for repayment of the debtor's debt cannot be qualified under article 165 of the Criminal Code, but under certain conditions should be considered as arbitrariness (article 229 of the Criminal Code). The demand for interest on the debt forms the composition of extortion, if the payment of these interests has not been agreed upon in advance by the debtor and the creditor [3].

The problem of solving extortion and arbitrariness often arises when the claim arises from the contractual relationship that previously bound the subject and the victim (loan, supply of goods, provision of services, harm, etc.). In qualifying these situations, the following approach has been developed: if coercion concerns only the property in respect of which the victim really has certain rights unfulfilled obligations, then arbitrariness is on the face. If, in addition, the claim relates to property that the subject claims unlawfully (a large amount, previously unspecified interest, specific personal belongings of the victim), the

act, if there are appropriate signs, constitutes extortion. At the same time, extortion cannot be considered coercion to transfer property, the value of which is increased by the real inflation index[4], the demand for interest on untimely amounts returned, if these percentages correspond to the established bank rate [5].

References:

1. Liability of individuals (Article 17 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan). <https://lex.uz/docs/111457#152526>
2. Rustambayev M.H. Course of criminal law of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The special part. Volume 4. Crimes in the field of economics, ecology, against the functioning of government bodies, management and public associations. Textbook for universities. 2nd edition, supplemented. – T.: Military Technical Institute of the National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2018. – p.41.
3. Paragraph 12 of the Resolution of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 17, 1998 No. 11 "On some issues that have arisen in judicial practice in cases of crimes in the field of economics." (as amended and supplemented by resolutions of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 14, 2002 No. 10, October 25, 2002 No. 28 and February 3, 2006 No. 5).<https://lex.uz/docs/1443982>
4. Gaukhman L.D., Maximov St. Responsibility for crimes against property. M.: Uch.-consult. the Yurinform Center. 1997.P.126
5. Safonov V.N. Organized extortion (criminal law and criminological aspects): Author's thesis. ... cand. Jurid. Sciences. St. Petersburg: St. Petersburg Academy of Sciences. THE Ministry OF Internal Affairs OF THE Russian Federation. 1997. p.20; Skoblikov P.A. Debt collection and organized crime. M.: Jurist. 1997. C.I8-19.
6. S.S.Niyozova. Prevention of Crime in the Family and the Role of Victimology in the Republic of Uzbekistan. International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology Vol. 29, No. 3, (2020), p. 3962.
7. Niyozova, S.S. (2020). The role of the victim in crimes committed by the violence of the person. Electronic Journal of Legal Research, 2 (5).